

Southern California CSUF DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

ADAPTATION OF THE EDINBURGH POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION
SCALE FOR VIETNAMESE AMERICANS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Thu Anh Pham

Doctoral Project Committee:

Beth Keely, PhD, RN, Project Chair
Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC, Committee Member

2015

Copyright Thu Anh Pham 2015 ©

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this project was to translate and adapt an existing postpartum depression tool, the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), into Vietnamese for use with Vietnamese Americans. This project required a two-stage approach. The first stage focused on the translation process, which emphasized cultural sensitivity and linguistic appropriateness while retaining the sensitivity of the instrument. The second stage involved a pilot study to test the validity and applicability of the translated instrument. A total of 34 women returning for a 6-week postpartum checkup at two community clinics were recruited and completed two questionnaires. Data collected via the Vietnamese EPDS was compared with the Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS), a validated depression instrument for the Vietnamese population. A correlation coefficient, $r = .935$, indicated that the two measures (VEPDS and VDS) were highly correlated. A cut-off score of 9/10 on the VEPDS was used as the benchmark for suspected postpartum depression. The prevalence of postpartum depression among Vietnamese American women in this project was 29%. Factors that significantly predicted depression in the Vietnamese women were being unemployed, being single, having some college education, and having a complication during pregnancy. The results indicated that the VEPDS was applicable and beneficial to use for screening for postpartum depression among Vietnamese American women.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	iii
LIST OF TABLES	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
DEDICATION	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	xix
BACKGROUND	1
Needs Assessment and Problem Statement	1
Purpose of the Project	3
Conceptual Framework	4
LITERATURE REVIEW	9
METHODS	14
Ethical Considerations	14
Translation and Cross-Cultural Adaptation Process	15
Tool Development	17
Pilot Study	18
Pilot Study	18
Setting	18
Instruments	19
Demographic Survey	19
Vietnamese EPDS (VEPDS)	19
Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS)	20
Procedure for Data Collection	20
Data Analysis	21
RESULTS	22
DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION	29
Limitations	31
Clinical Implications	31

Conclusions.....	32
Clinical Practice Change.....	33
REFERENCES	34
APPENDIX A: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	37
APPENDIX B: EDINBURG POSTNATAL DEPRESSION SCALE (EPDS)	54
APPENDIX C: CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN PILOT STUDY	56
APPENDIX D: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA SURVEY	58
APPENDIX E: VIETNAMESE EDINBURG POSTNATAL DEPRESSION SCALE (VEPDS).....	59

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Basic Demographics of Survey Sample.....	23
2. Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) Internal Consistency Calculation: Cronbach's Alpha Results	26
3. Correlation Between Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) and Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS)	27
4. Explanation of the Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) Score by Regression Model	28

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Perceptions of Vietnamese American child-bearing women about postpartum depression	8
2. Percentage and frequency distributions for the Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS)	25

DEDICATION

To my husband, Hoang Nguyen, and my children, Harrison, Ruth, Hope,
Jacob, and Faith, whose love, concern, and encouragement
have never ceased throughout this project.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project would have not been accomplished without the help of many individuals who guided and supported my efforts from beginning to end.

I express my immense gratitude to my project committee, Dr. Keely and Dr. Brady. They provided guidance, knowledge, and encouragement throughout. I could not have asked for more competent and supportive faculty.

I am particularly indebted to those who assisted me in the data collection process, especially Phuong Pham, BSN, RN. I am thankful to Phuong for her support throughout the data collection process.

Finally, I am most appreciative of my husband, Dr. Hoang Nguyen, for his expert consultation on the tool development process. I am extremely grateful for his continuous input and support throughout the process of this project.

BACKGROUND

Needs Assessment and Problem Statement

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a significant mental illness that can affect every childbearing woman, regardless of race, ethnicity, or background. PPD refers to a constellation of depressive symptoms that occur after childbirth. The American Psychiatric Association (APA) describes PPD in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders V (DSM-V)* as depression that occurs within the first 4 weeks after delivery (APA, 2013). Symptoms of PPD are decreased appetite, insomnia, fatigue, loss of pleasure, and, in some serious cases, thoughts of suicide (Miller & LaRusso, 2011). This mental illness is reported to be the leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality in new mothers (Clay & Seehusen, 2004). PPD affects not only the mother and infant but all members of the family (Camp, 2013). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) conducted a survey regarding depression among women of reproductive age in the United States and found that 19% had experienced postpartum depression (CDC, 2010). However, there is insufficient information about this illness among various Asian and Pacific Islander racial/ethnic groups.

Vietnamese Americans (VAs) are one of the fastest-growing minority populations in the United States. According to 2010 census data, the VA population experienced a 38% increase in growth in the past 10 years. Approximately 50% of VAs reside in California, with the majority residing in Orange County (U.S. Bureau of the Census, 2010). Even though there is a growing number of VAs, there are insufficient data on the prevalence of PPD in this population, most likely due to lack of a culturally appropriate

screening tool for PPD for health care providers to use. Without an assessment tool, screening does not occur.

Depression is an illness that is rarely discussed in the VA population. Asian mothers are less likely to report depressive symptoms because mental illness is highly stigmatized in Asian cultures (Goyal, Wang, Shen, Wong, & Palaniappan, 2012). Because social functioning and traditional interdependent relationships are important values in Asian cultures, including Vietnamese ethnicity, VA women prefer to embrace the whole extended family in the medical decision-making process. This process hinders their willingness to share openly about their depressive symptoms. It also creates additional stress that can potentially affect the women's mental well-being (Fancher, Ton, Meyer, Ho, & Paterniti, 2010).

Vietnamese people believe that the expression of depressive symptoms is a sign of immaturity or weakness (Nieme, Malqvist, Giang, Allebeck, & Falkenberg, 2013). Because of this stigmatization, VA women want to save face for themselves and their family (Fancher et al., 2010). Yet, PPD is a significant illness in the Asian population. Huang and Mathers (2001) reported that about 40% of Taiwanese women had depression in the first 6 weeks after delivery. Although the study focused on the Taiwanese population, it may be applicable to the Vietnamese population because these two groups share similarities both culturally and in birthing rituals and routines.

Several screening tools for PPD are available to use in primary care settings, with most health care providers using the Edinburgh Postpartum Depression scale (EPDS) or the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ). However, these tools were designed and developed to be used in the Western culture; they are not culturally sensitive to signs and

symptoms of depression in the Asian population (Klainin & Arthur, 2009). In addition, symptoms of illness are interpreted through a cultural context, leading to even more difficulty in detecting this illness in non-Western cultures (Fancher et al., 2010).

There is some research that indicates somatic symptoms should be considered when screening for depression in the Asian American. In a literature review focusing on factors that influence screening depression among Vietnamese population, Niemi et al. (2013) found that somatic symptoms were the primary distress symptoms experienced by Vietnamese people with depression. The lack of an appropriate screening tool may be an important contributor to underdiagnosis of PPD in this population. Therefore, there is a need for a culturally sensitive screening tool to be used in assessing VA women so that health care providers can provide effective preventive care and treatment for VA women diagnosed with PPD.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this project was to develop a culturally sensitive, linguistically appropriate Vietnamese-adapted translation of the EPDS for use in the VA population. The adaptation process used in this project took into consideration cultural differences in depressive symptoms, which enhanced the validity of the adapted EPDS for the VA population. Likewise, linguistic appropriateness was examined by consulting with experts in mental health who are skilled translators or cultural brokers in both the Vietnamese and English languages. Furthermore, the process focused on maintaining fidelity with the EPDS, especially with regard to assuring sensitivity of the instrument for PPD through forward and backward translations to maintain similarity in constructs of

the original and adapted instruments. In addition, a pilot study ($n = 34$) was conducted to test the validity of the instruments.

By developing a valid and reliable adaption of the EPDS for use in the VA population, this author is seeking to assist health care providers in identifying VA women with PPD. In addition, it is anticipated that there will be increased awareness of the existence of PPD in the VA population when the adapted VA EPDS is used in this population.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework that was adapted for this project is the Health Belief Model (HBM), which is one of the most effective and commonly used theories to explain health conditions and human behaviors. The HBM examines the relationships among belief, knowledge, and decision making (Yoo, Kwon, & Pfeiffer, 2013). This model is widely used in public health to predict preventive health behavior, identify health risk, and describe sick role behavior (Abram & Sheeran, 2005). By conceptualizing a condition such as the PPD in the context of the HBM, the clinician can gain the support of women in the prevention and treatment of PPD (Yoo et al., 2013).

There are four core constructs in the HBM. The first construct is perceived susceptibility, which refers to a person's belief about his or her susceptibility to a specific health risk. Each person discerns his or her chance to acquire a particular illness or destructive condition based on personal belief. Each person can also demonstrate a wide range of discernment about health, ranging from complete denial about any possibility of acquiring an illness to complete belief in the inevitability of having the illness. According to this model, a person is more likely to engage in taking preventive measures

when the person feels that he/she is highly susceptible (Rosenstock, 1974). VA women usually believe that depression is mostly a Western culture illness (Fancher et al., 2010). This belief makes it difficult for VA women to think that they are just as susceptible to PPD as are others. By encouraging discussion related to the illness and educating women about the physiologic aspect of depression, the clinician will be able to increase awareness of the signs/symptoms of depression. This awareness, in turn, will help VA women to understand their susceptibility to PPD. By increasing awareness of PPD, a change in perception of susceptibility will occur in the VA population whereby they will realize that postpartum VA women are also vulnerable to this condition.

The second construct is perceived severity, referring to a person's belief about the magnitude of an illness and its consequences. Display of this belief also varies from individual to individual. One person may look at severity of the illness through its medical manifestations, such as the temporary signs and symptoms of the illness to its potential mortality. Others may define severity as the adverse effects of the illness on family, job, and relationship. The combination of perceived susceptibility and perceived severity is referred to as the perception of threat (Rosenstock, 1974). Research suggests an association between newborns' weight gain and mothers with depression (Gress-Smith, Luecken, Lemery-Chalfant, & Howe, 2012). VA women with PPD are more likely to realize the severity of this illness and its possible impact on their newborn's health, weight, and sleep when clinicians emphasize the seriousness of changes in mood or emotion that mothers may experience after childbirth. According to the HBM, until one perceives the severity of the depression symptoms and the adverse effects on one's family, one is unlikely to seek help from health care providers or others.

The third construct is perceived benefits. This refers to a belief in the benefit of health-promoting behavior to decrease the risk of illness. If one believes that a particular action will reduce one's susceptibility and severity to the illness, one is more likely to engage in an effective and beneficial action. The construct, perceived barriers, refers to belief in the inconvenience of an action required to reduce the risk of illness. Barriers such as cost, pain, and unpleasantness will hinder people from taking action to reduce the risk of illness (Rosenstock, 1974). With a culturally sensitive tool for PPD that can be used to screen VA women, clinicians will experience the benefit of early detection of PPD by a decrease in the severity and complications of this illness. Adequate information about barriers, such as cost of treatment or fear of being diagnosed with a mental illness, could also be addressed by clinicians at the time of screening.

The HBM theorizes that a trigger is essential to engage in health-promoting behavior. Cues of action are the triggers that make a person realize the need to take action. These cues may be internal, such as a headache or pain, or external, such as knowing a friend with the illness or receiving information about the illness from a trustworthy source. For example, a person may consider taking preventive action when a health threat is perceived. But until the person perceives that the benefits of the preventive action outweigh the barriers, the person is not likely to take action (Yoo et al., 2013).

Perceptions of health-related behavior can be affected by a variety of modifying factors, including demographic variables and psychosocial characteristics (Abram & Sheeran, 2005). Common demographic variables include age, ethnicity, and education. Psychosocial variables include personality, culture, group pressure, and family dynamic.

In addition, self-efficacy—the confidence in one’s ability to pursue a positive outcome—is one of the key concepts of the HBM that can affect health-related behavior (Rosenstock, Strecher, & Becker, 1988).

Modifying factors that influence the perception of PPD among VA are stigmatization and face saving, social functioning and family dynamic, traditional healing and beliefs about medications, and language and culture (Fancher et al., 2010). For VA women with PPD, these factors can represent barriers to seeking help. Understanding these concepts will help clinicians to identify the risk factors for PPD and provide intervention when needed. For example, the traditional interdependence relationship associated with the Vietnamese culture is a modifiable factor in this population if one is aware of it. By simply including family members in the screening process, the clinician can encourage VA women to respond to the screening questionnaire.

Language is another readily modifiable factor. Using the appropriate language can have a substantial role in helping VA women to fully comprehend the severity of PPD and the benefits of seeking help to treat PPD. By communicating with these women in their native language, the clinician can facilitate effective communication and enhance the ability of these women to describe their symptoms of PPD to the health care provider (Nieme et al., 2013). In short, VA women are more likely participate in the screening process if they are able to complete a self-reported questionnaire in Vietnamese. Unfortunately, there is currently no validated screening tool for assessing PPD in Vietnamese women (Figure 1).

The HBM provided the underpinning of a conceptual model that this nurse practitioner used in this project that focused on adaptation and translation of the EPDS

Figure 1. Perceptions of Vietnamese American child-bearing women about postpartum depression.

screening tool for PPD. The language and terminology used in the screening tool were designed to emphasize the perception of susceptibility and severity of PPD. The revision process emphasized the modifiable factors mentioned to increase the validity of the screening tool. In summary, the author's goal was development of a culturally acceptable screening tool to identify depressive symptoms that captured Vietnamese cultural considerations and language. These factors are key components in providing prevention and appropriate timing of treatment of PPD in the VA population.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature search was conducted using the following criteria: (a) screening tools for PPD and Vietnamese or Asian, (b) articles written in English, (c) articles relevant to the topic at hand, and (d) articles published from 2005 through 2013. Search databases included PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsychINFO. By using the keywords *screening tools/scales* and *depression/postpartum depression*, this search identified 18 publications related to this project. Including the word *Asian* to the search added two publications. Changing the word *Asian* to *Vietnamese* returned the message “no publications found.” Reference mining from the cited publications revealed 10 additional publications on PPD in the Asian population and provided additional publications on the sensitivity/specificity and validation of the PPD screening tools used in the Western population.

A combined PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsychINFO search using the key words *validation of PPD screening tools and Vietnamese* revealed no publications. Changing the term *Vietnamese* to *Asian* produced 10 publications. Searching from reference lists of the retrieved publications produced five publications related to the topic of depression in the Vietnamese population. Due to the overall lack of information on validated screening tools for PPD in the Vietnamese population, publications associated with the Asian population dating back to 2000 were accepted if they used a validated screening tool for PPD in their respective language. There were three articles investigating translated PPD screening tools in the Thai, Chinese, and Taiwanese populations.

Another combined PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsychINFO search using the terms *screening tools for PPD* and *culture* did not reveal any further publications. However, using the terms *postpartum depression and culture* returned 15 publications. These publications were narrowed to the following outcomes of interest: (a) studies that reported validity and reliability of screening tools for PPD; (b) screening tools used in the Asian, specifically Vietnamese, population; (c) the need to screen for PPD; and (d) cultural aspects of depressive symptomatology. Of the 60 publications identified, 18 met the criteria and were used for evidence in this paper.

Appendix A includes the tables of evidence used for literature synthesis. All articles were critiqued, revealing that PPD is a serious universal health condition that affects new mothers most frequently within 12 weeks after delivery. It is recognized as one of the most frequent forms of maternal morbidity across all race and ethnic groups (Dennis, 2004; McQueen, Montgomery, Lappan-Gracon, Evans, & Hunter, 2008; Youn & Jeong, 2011; Zubaran, Schumacher, Roxo, & Foresti, 2010). However, paucity of research on PPD in racial/ethnic groups, including the various Asian populations, was noted in the literature (Goyal et al., 2012); specifically, there are no publications on PPD in the VA population.

All of the articles reported that the etiology for PPD is unclear. However, researchers have identified factors that may increase the risk of PPD. Biological factors such as a personal or family history of depression are consistently cited as positive predictors for PPD. Psychological variables, including stressful life events and inadequate social support, can increase the risk of PPD (Miller & LaRusso, 2011). In-law family conflicts, lack of job security, and economic difficulties are social factors

that are associated with PPD in the VA population (Nieme et al., 2013). Other risk factors that have been identified in the Asian population are young maternal age and the birth of a female infant (Zubaran et al., 2010). Restricting physical activity is a cultural factor that increases risk for PPD (Holroyd, Chan, Lopez, & Chen, 2013). Assessing for risk factors and screening for symptoms of PPD are considered to be cost effective and efficient in identifying and caring for women with this mental illness (Evins & Theofrastous, 1997). The development of a culturally sensitive screening tool to identify depressive symptoms was described in various studies as one of the key elements in providing timely treatment for PPD (Lee et al., 1998; Pitanupong, Liabsuetrakul, & Vittayanont, 2007; Teng et al., 2005).

Several instruments are used to screen for PPD in the Western population. However, the consensus from all of the reviewed articles was that the EPDS is the recommended self-report tool to confirm depression symptoms in postpartum mothers (Cox, Holden, & Sagovsky, 1987; Dennis, 2004; McQueen et al., 2008; Small, Lumley, & Yelland, 2003; Zubaran et al., 2010). Cox et al. (1987) developed the EPDS in 1987. It contains 10 items that correspond to various clinical depression symptoms. The maximum score is 30, with a higher score correlating with increasing depressive symptoms (Cox et al., 1987). Its reliability, sensitivity, and specificity as an instrument to screen for PPD in clinical practice have been established in several studies (Cox et al., 1987; Dennis, 2004; McQueen et al., 2008). The EPDS validation study done by Cox et al. reported sensitivity at 86% and specificity at 78%, with the cut-off scores of 9/10 (Cox et al., 1987). This tool is accepted and used internationally. It has been translated into

many languages and tested worldwide (Pitanupong et al., 2007). However, it has not been translated into Vietnamese.

A literature search revealed three articles related to the translation and validation of the EPDS tools in Thai, Chinese, and Taiwanese (Lee et al., 1998; Pitanupong et al., 2007; Teng et al., 2005). No articles on the translation and validation of EPDS in Vietnamese were found. All translated versions of EPDS reported that certain questions were difficult to translate because the concept addressed in that particular question was unfamiliar in the Asian culture. For example, direct translation for Item 6 in the EPDS (“things have been getting on top of me”) was problematic as that concept is difficult to understand and rather uncommon in Thai, Chinese, and Taiwanese (Lee et al., 1998; Pitanupong et al., 2007; Teng et al., 2005). All of the researchers involved in these translation studies agreed that a culturally and linguistically appropriate instrument is essential for early detection of PPD in the Asian population.

Another important finding from the Lee et al. (1998), Teng et al. (2005), and Pitanupong et al. (2007) articles focused on the evidence that PPD symptoms are usually expressed in terms of somatic symptoms in the Asian population. This is found to be true in the VA population as well. A study conducted by Niemi et al. in a Vietnamese population reported that Vietnamese patients usually described depression symptoms using the term *neurasthenia*, which is a set of complex symptoms characterized by chronic fatigue and generalized aches and pains (Nieme et al., 2013). Kinzie et al. (1982) developed the Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS) to screen for depression among Vietnamese refugees who arrived in the United State in the early 1980s. They suggested that the differences in symptoms reported in the VA population validated that health care

providers must search for a more culturally sensitive tool for PPD screening in Asian populations. Wong, Wu, Guo, Lam, and Snowden (2012) recommend that a socioculturally, language-specific screening tool be used for prevention and detection of PPD in the Chinese population.

METHODS

Analyzing how depression is manifested and expressed cross-culturally is not a forthright process. This section describes two stages in the process of forming a culturally sensitive depression screening tool. The first stage consisted of translating and modifying an existing tool, the EPDS (Appendix B). The second stage required the author to conduct a pilot study to validate the Vietnamese-adapted EPDS (VEPDS).

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) at the California State University, Long Beach (CSULB), reviewed this project for protection of human subjects and gave approval. A letter of support was provided from the clinics where data were collected. Certain ethical considerations were addressed, even though the general population of VA women who participated in the reliability and validity testing of this tool was not anticipated to be a vulnerable group. The ethical considerations included informed consent, privacy, confidentiality, and beneficence.

Included with the study packet given to the project participants was a cover letter, written informed consent (Appendix C), the demographic survey (Appendix D, designed by the investigator), the final version of the VEPDS (Appendix E), and a Vietnamese depression screening scale. The cover letter presented a brief description of the research project and stressed the importance of signing the consent form. Privacy of the collected information was maintained by not recording any name or identifiable information on any questionnaire and by using the information collected only for this project. To maintain confidentiality, the investigator was the only person to access the data. The data were stored in a locked, separated area; the computer in which the data were stored was

encrypted with a protected password and identification number. All data will be destroyed upon completion of this project.

The cover letter, consent form, and demographic survey were translated to Vietnamese by the investigator and reviewed by two health care providers who are fluent in both Vietnamese and English. The investigator is a Vietnamese American nurse practitioner who works with VA women in the community. She is fluent in both languages. All of the above forms were reviewed and approved by the CSULB IRB Committee.

Translation and Cross-Cultural Adaptation Process

The EPDS is a 10-item, self-report, yes/no questionnaire developed to identify women with postpartum depression symptoms (Cox et al., 1987). The items on the questionnaire are designed to screen for symptoms of depression such as sleep difficulty, low energy, anhedonia, and suicidal ideation. Items 1, 2, and 4 seek information about the respondent's ability to enjoy life. Items 3 and 5 ask about guilt feelings. Item 10 inquires about suicidal ideation. The respondent is asked to check the response that is closest to her feelings during the past 7 days. It is important for the respondent to complete the questionnaire by herself, without help of others that could affect the accuracy of the test. This is especially cogent for Vietnamese women because they tend to hide their true feeling around others. A score of 10 or greater indicates increasing depressive symptoms.

Written permission is not required when the EPDS is adapted or translated to another language because it is considered public domain by the developers (Cox et al., 1987). Appropriate citations as to the authorship of the EPDS are provided in this paper.

A copy of the English version of the EPDS is included in Appendix B. According to Hilton and Skrutkowski (2002), the process of translation and cross-cultural adaptation has several steps. Step 1 is the process of forward translation. In this step, the items are translated from English to Vietnamese. In this project, the forward translation was performed by two independent bilingual translators whose first language is Vietnamese. One of the translators is a nurse practitioner and the author of this study; the other translator is a certified court translator. In this process, the translators utilized the HBM approach to create the necessary conceptual and linguistic modifications to make the scale sensitive to the VA culture. The resulting translations were named T1 and T2, respectively.

Step 2 is synthesis of the translation process. Two translators and another community nurse practitioner went through each translation questionnaire and reviewed any differences. All variances were discussed to reach agreement, and one forward translation version called T-12 was produced.

Step 3 requires back translation into English. The main focus of this step is to ensure that the translated version still retains the concept of the original language. The two back translators were teachers whose first language was English and who did not have any medical background. They translated the T-12 version, which resulted in two back translations, BT1 and BT2.

Step 4 is the revision process to develop the final version of the scale. All translated versions (T1, T2, T-12, B1, and B2) were reviewed and consolidated into one final version. The revisions were performed by all four translators. Each item was

reviewed individually to compare the linguistic validity. Any discrepancy was discussed and resolved to reach consensus.

Step 5 is the process of evaluating face validity and content validity of the Vietnamese-adapted EPDS. A panel of experts participated in the evaluation process: a psychiatrist, a social worker who is clinical director at a Vietnamese County Mental Health division, and a psychologist. All of these experts are bilingual in Vietnamese and English. They expressed opinions on whether each item truly reflected the symptoms of depression. In addition, they provided input on items that needed further revision. The final version of Vietnamese EPDS was then used in the project's pilot study.

Tool Development

The translation process encountered multiple linguistic difficulties. Item 6 of the EPDS, "Things have been getting on top of me," required extensive translation with a detailed explanation because there was no direct equivalence or literal translation for this colloquial English expression. After much consideration and consultation with mental health experts, this item was translated as "Things became unbearable for me." This translation ensured that the expression was culturally meaningful in the context of the VA population. Item 8 of the EPDS, "I have felt sad or miserable," was used to express a depressed or sad mood. Unfortunately, this concept is not familiar to the Vietnamese culture and was difficult to translate. After deliberation, this item was adapted to reflect the Vietnamese concept of depression, which leaned toward a more somatic expression of symptoms, such as pain all over the body. The final translation for Item 8 was, "I felt sad and my body aches unreasonably." Item 10 of the EPDS, "The thought of harming myself has occurred to me" was used to assess suicidal ideation. VA women tend to

perceive that the infant's life and their lives are one. Therefore, this question was adapted to, "The thought of harming myself and my baby has occurred to me." The final version of this tool is included as Appendix E.

Pilot Study

The goal of the pilot study was to evaluate the scale's applicability, validity, and internal consistency. The VEPDS was developed to identify asymptomatic VA women who may have PPD. It was essential that the scale be relevant to this population. Several measurement were used to determine the applicability of the VEPDS. The changes in perception of depression and acceptance of depression symptoms by participants demonstrated the applicability of the scale. The validity of the scale (the ability to identify depressive participants) was assessed. Internal consistency (correlation between test items that are created to measure the same construct) was analyzed.

Sample

A convenience sample composed of women ranging from 21 to 43 years old who had given birth 4 to 8 weeks earlier was recruited to participate in the study. About 50 patients from two local private practices in southern California were recruited. The participants were fluent in Vietnamese and/or bilingual in English and Vietnamese. The participants had been seen by the health care providers at either of the two clinics participating in this study during their pregnancy and had returned to the clinic for postpartum checkup.

Setting

The participants were recruited from two private practices in southern California that serve a population that is predominately VA. The clinics had specialty areas of

family practice, internal medicine, and obstetrics and gynecology medicine. All participants were directed to a private area in the waiting room of the clinics to complete the questionnaires while waiting for their appointment. They were instructed to deposit the signed informed consent in the box labeled “Consent Forms” and deposit the completed questionnaires in the box labeled “Survey.” The boxes were located in the waiting area where they could be easily seen by participants.

Instruments

Demographic Survey

Demographic data were collected to describe the population. The survey (Appendix D) gathered the respondent’s age, marital status, highest educational level, employment status, living condition (with or without extended family), length of stay in America, and preferred language. Obstetric variables were also included in the survey: number of pregnancies, route of current delivery, and complications during labor or delivery. These factors were included in the pilot study for data collection purposes because they were identified in the literature as associated with PPD.

Vietnamese EPDS (VEPDS)

The self-administered 10-item VEPDS gathered data concerning signs and symptoms of depression. Participants were encouraged to complete the questionnaire alone, without input from family members. This author identified a total score of 10 or greater as associated with possible depression, based on the score of 10 that is the benchmark used for the EPDS. The maximum possible score is 13.

Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS)

The VDS was developed and validated by Kinzie et al. (1982) for use with newly arrived Vietnamese refugees. This scale was developed to help with depression diagnosis in both adult males and females. This scale contains 15 items that assess psychophysiological symptoms derived from the *DSM-III-R* and include specific Vietnamese expressions of cognitive, affective, and somatic symptoms of depression. A total score of 14 or more correlated with a clinical diagnosis of depression. The VDS has been validated and used widely in research about screening for depression in the Vietnamese population. However, this tool is not specific for PPD. The VDS was used in this study to help establish the validity of the VEPDS. Permission to use the VDS was granted by Dr. Kinzie through email communication.

Procedure for Data Collection

Packages containing a cover letter, informed consent form, demographic survey, copies of the two instruments mentioned in the survey section of this paper, and a list of community mental health resources were available at the two practice settings. The front office staff members approached patients who had returned to clinic for postpartum checkup and recruited them to participate in the pilot study. The front office staff members were trained by the investigator to explain the study and obtain consent. Participants were asked to complete the self-report VEPDS and the VDS in a private area before or while waiting for their routine postpartum check-up. All forms were returned to a lock box located in the waiting areas. The investigator collected all forms at the end of each working day during the duration of data collection (i.e., four weeks). All forms were kept in a specific and confidential folder in a locked cabinet at a business office at

the investigator's personal residence. Data were personally entered in the investigator's computer by the investigator for analysis. Data were reviewed by a statistician during analysis and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 20.0 (SPSS).

Data Analysis

The demographic data were reviewed separately by the investigator to identify variants that could affect responses to the survey. This analysis helped to evaluate the cultural sensitivity of the VEPDS. A Cronbach's alpha was calculated to measure the internal consistency of the scale and to determine whether any of the 10 items in the scale could be discarded. In addition, a multitrait matrix was performed to determine whether there was a correlation between VEPDS and VDS scores. This comparison was used to determine the construct validity of the VEPDS.

RESULTS

The questionnaire packages were given to 50 women initially indicated a desire to participate in the study during the time from November 12, 2014, to December 12, 2014. A total of 34 completed questionnaires were returned to the collection box at the clinic, for a return rate of 68%. These 34 completed questionnaires were used in the analysis process. The basic demographic characteristics of the 34 participants are listed in Table 1.

The mean age of the 34 participants was 30 years, with a range from 21 to 43 years. There were 6 (18%) women whose age was 35 years or more. Twenty-nine participants (85%) were married and 5 (15%) were single. All participants reported a high school education, with 26 (76%) having a college education. The mean number of years in America was 10, with a range from 1 year to 23 years. Seventeen women (50%) reported unemployment, and 16 (47%) were primigravidas. All listed Vietnamese as their preferred language. Twenty-four (71%) lived at home with parents or in-laws and other relatives as extended family. Two women had had a cesarean section and 32 (94%) had had normal spontaneous vaginal deliveries. One woman reported complications during delivery. Ten women (29%) had VEPDS scores of 10 and above, which indicated signs and symptoms of depression after giving birth to their babies. Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of scores at various levels (e.g., four had scores of 4 up to 5).

A Cronbach's coefficient alpha was calculated to measure the internal consistency of the VEPDS resulted in a coefficient of 0.7 (Table 2). A standardized Cronbach's alpha of 0.7 is associated with good internal consistency or intercorrelation among test items. A correlation matrix was constructed to measure the correlation between the VEPDS and

Table 1

Basic Demographics of Survey Sample (N = 34)

Variable and category	<i>n</i>	%
Age		
21	1	3
22	3	9
23	1	3
25	1	3
26	2	6
27	1	3
28	1	3
29	2	6
30	2	6
31	4	12
32	5	15
33	1	3
34	4	12
35	3	9
36	1	3
39	1	3
43	1	3
Marital status		
Married	29	85
Single	5	15
Educational level		
High school	8	24
College	26	76
Employment status		
Full time	16	47
Half time	1	3
Unemployed	17	50
Length of stay in United States		
1–5 years	6	17
6–9 years	14	41
10–15 years	8	24
16–20 years	3	9
> 20 years	3	9
Preferred language		
Vietnamese	34	100
English	0	0

Table 1 (continued)

Variable and category	<i>n</i>	%
Living condition		
Own family	10	29
Extended family	24	71
Number of pregnancies		
1	16	47
2	13	38
3	3	9
4	2	6
Complications during pregnancy and delivery		
Yes	1	3
No	33	97
Route of current delivery		
Normal vaginal	32	94
Caesarean	2	6

the VDS. The correlation coefficient, $r = .935$, indicated that the two measures were highly correlated (Table 3) and provided evidence supporting the use of the VEPDS as a valid test for depression in the Vietnamese population. In addition, a regression model was developed to predict the significance of demographic variables in explaining the VEPDS score and the VDS score (Table 4). The results showed that significant factors related to depression were being single, college education, unemployment, and having a complication of pregnancy. Unemployment was the most significant factor in explaining the VEPDS scores.

Figure 2. Percentage and frequency distributions for the Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS).

Table 2

Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) Internal Consistency Calculation: Cronbach's Alpha Results

Item	Raw alpha	Standard alpha	G6(smc)	Average r	S/N	Alpha se
Age	0.53	0.65	0.77	0.28	1.9	0.16
Education	0.58	0.67	0.80	0.29	2.0	0.15
Years in US	0.57	0.65	0.78	0.28	1.9	0.15
Pregnancies	0.58	0.66	0.79	0.28	1.9	0.15
EPDS	0.50	0.67	0.68	0.29	2.0	0.17
VDS	0.49	0.65	0.66	0.27	1.8	0.17

Note: Reliability analysis for Cronbach's alpha: raw alpha = .059, standard alpha = 0.7, G6(smc) = 0.81, average r = 0.28, S/N = 2.3, ase = 0.14, mean = 11, SD = 2.4; 95% confidence boundaries = 0.32, 0.59, 0.86.

Table 3

Correlation Between Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) and Vietnamese Depression Scale (VDS)

	Age	Education	Years in US	Pregnancies	VEPDS	VDS
Age	1.00	0.29	0.48	0.56	0.66	0.06
Education	0.29	1.00	0.53	0.16	0.11	0.19
Years in US	0.48	0.54	1.00	0.28	0.05	0.07
Pregnancies	0.56	0.16	0.28	1.00	0.17	0.23
VEPDS	0.07	0.11	0.05	0.17	1.00	0.94*
VDS	0.06	0.19	0.08	0.23	0.94	1.00

Note. US = United States, VEPDS = Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale, VDS = Vietnamese Depression Scale .

*Correlation coefficient $r = .935$.

Table 4

Explanation of the Vietnamese Edinburg Postpartum Depression Scale (VEPDS) Score by Regression Model

Item	Estimate	SE	t	Pr (> t)
Age	0.15	0.19	0.81	.426
Factor, Marital Status: married	-44.93	16.19	-2.77	.011
Factor, Marital Status: single	-40.85	14.59	-2.80	.010*
Educational status	3.18	1.09	2.92	.008**
Factor, Employment: half time	2.62	3.66	0.72	.481
Factor, Employment: unemployed	6.30	1.39	4.52	.000***
Years in America	-0.14	0.14	-1.05	0.307
Factor, Living Situation: husband	-0.88	1.99	-0.44	.665
Factor, Living Situation: unit	-2.98	2.00	-1.50	.149
Number of pregnancies	0.50	0.91	0.56	.583
Factor, Complication of Pregnancy: yes	11.75	4.49	2.62	.016*
Factor, Route of Delivery: NVD	-0.61	2.99	-0.21	.840
Factor, Route of Deliver: VD	NA	NA	NA	NA

Note. NVD = nonvaginal delivery, VD = vaginal delivery.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION

PPD is a significant condition affecting women's health globally. Researchers have emphasized the need for a culturally sensitive and linguistically appropriate screening tool for use in the VA population. This project is the first attempt to adapt and translate the EPDS into the Vietnamese language. The tool that emerged from this study, the VEPDS, underwent pilot testing to measure the instrument's applicability, validity, and internal consistency. The findings showed that the VEPDS was a beneficial instrument to screen for PPD in the VA population.

In this study population, the cutoff point of 9/10 was established as a positive depression score that would require attention and possible intervention by health care providers. Ten of the participants (29%) had scores indicating signs and symptoms of depression. There are several explanations for this prevalence rate in the study sample, which was higher than expected. Although the reported prevalence of PPD is approximately 19% among women in the United States, there are no current prevalence data available for the VA population (CDC, 2010). One might postulate that the VEPDS score of 9/10 overestimates PPD. However, it is possible that this percentage is accurate because the prevalence of PPD in non-Western countries has been reported to range from 5 to 60% (Affonso, De, Horowitz, & Mayberry, 2000), the higher incidence in this study may in fact be a true reflection of the incidence of PPD in the VA population.

Further studies are needed to determine whether a cutoff score of 9/10 on the VEPDS does indeed reflect an elevated false positive result or a true positive score. Lee et al. (1998) also noted that the cutoff score of 9/10 used in their study may have yielded a high rate of false positive. The prevalence of PPD can vary depending on the study

population, cutoff score, and time of study (Boyd, Le, & Somberg, 2005). Therefore, the VEPDS should be validated in other settings before being disseminated and used as a valid instrument. As a consideration in this study, a valid and reliable screening tool by its purpose should not miss the factor of concern (in this case, postpartum depression) but not refer excessively based on false positive scores.

Logistic regression analysis indicated that marital status, education level, employment status, and complications during pregnancy were significant factors in predicting VEPDS scores. The high prevalence of PPD among unemployed women in this study can be interpreted to indicate that employment may be a protective factor for depression; however, there are other interpretations for this effect (e.g., unemployment may be a proxy measure for low socioeconomic status in this study). There is a paucity of published literature exploring the relationship between employment and PPD. Research by Hock and DeMeis (1990) suggested that maternal attitudes, beliefs, and preference in employment can affect postpartum women. Unfortunately, the demographic data collected for this project did not include the overall socioeconomic status of the family or prior employment status. The significant effect of employment noted in this project could be related to the fact that these VA women may have contributed significant financial support for the family. Therefore, unemployment could be a significant stressor. Another explanation is that the additional financial burden of caring for the new infant in the face of unemployment created stress for these women in light of the family's socioeconomic status.

Limitations

Limitations to this pilot study are acknowledged. The findings may not be generalized because the project was conducted in only two local community clinics and thus the participants were not necessarily representative of the overall population of VA postpartum women. Convenience sampling produced a small sample size that represent bias in the data. There was no question in the VEPDS that sought information about the onset of the signs and symptoms of depression. The author did not follow up with any participant whose score related to symptomatology was 10 or above. The follow-up period was limited to the 6-weeks postpartum check-up, which may have affected the rate of PPD, as this mental health issue can appear for up to 12 months after birth. Other demographic and psychosocial data (e.g., income, wanted pregnancy) that might have indicated factors associated with PPD were not gathered.

Clinical Implications

In using the VEPDS for screening, 29% of the women in this study reported signs and symptoms of PPD at 6 weeks postpartum. Unemployment status was a strong predictor of PPD in this sample. However, it was not known whether the VA women had been employed previously but were currently unemployed as a result of the pregnancy and birth or whether they were unemployed before their pregnancy. Thus, the impact of employment should be studied further regarding its possible influence on PPD. The wording of this question should be reconsidered in future studies to clarify the time period of unemployment whether unemployment was voluntary or forced. The findings from this project regarding the appropriateness of the VEPDS as a screening tool are that (a) the VEPDS represents an adaption of the EPDS that underwent an extensive

translation process, (b) the VEPDS and the VDS are positively correlated, (c) 29% positive incidence of PPD is not outside the range of what one would expect, and (d) no other PPD tools have been translated to Vietnamese. Therefore, the results of this project support the use of the VEPDS as a tool for early detection and intervention of PPD if done so with caution. However, as noted before, additional validation of this tool is needed through replication studies with larger numbers of postpartum patients at other settings, as well as at female health care visits other than routine postpartum check-ups at 4 to 6 weeks. The VEPDS might also be tested in a pediatric setting with mothers who present their infants for 4- and 6-month well-child visits.

Conclusions

The VEPDS will assist in identifying postpartum women with symptoms of depression, enabling prompt diagnosis of this illness in clinical settings. There are multiple significant outcomes in providing a culturally sensitive EPDS. First, early identification will enhance early treatment and may produce better outcomes for both the woman and her child. Second, the existence of the VEPDS will most likely increase awareness of depression in the VA population, heretofore a mental health problem that is often unrecognized. Raising awareness of depression symptoms will also promote new perceptions about this illness. It is important to educate the VA population about the existence of depression and its impact on the woman, her family, and the community. Creation of a valid and reliable tool will facilitate discussion about depression between health care providers and VA women. Open communication will improve the relationship between health care providers and VA women. Future researchers can use

the VEPDS to investigate the prevalence of PPD and identify risks factors associated with depression among VA women.

Clinical Practice Change

Two clinical practice changes resulted from this project. Administrators of the two clinics where the study took place were informed of the results of the pilot study. They are now considering how to incorporate use of the VEPDS as part of the routine process of postpartum checkup. Even though the process of change might take time, health care providers in the clinics were made aware of the prevalence of PPD in VA women and were willing to open dialog with patients about this illness. Furthermore, the researcher plans to prepare a manuscript for publication and to disseminate the findings to local obstetricians and pediatricians who work with this population.

REFERENCES

- Abram, C., & Sheeran, P. (2005). The Health Belief Model. In M. Conner & P. Norman (Eds.), *Predicting health behavior* (pp. 28-79). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Affonso, D. D., De, A. K., Horowitz, J. A., & Mayberry, L. J. (2000). An international study exploring levels of postpartum depressive symptomatology. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research, 49*, 207-216.
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). Washington, D.C.: Author.
- Boyd, R. C., Le, H. N., & Somberg, R. (2005). Review of screening instruments for postpartum depression. *Archives of Women's Mental Health, 8*, 141-153.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2010). *Depression among women of reproductive age*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/reproductivehealth/depression/>
- Clay, E., & Seehusen, M. D. A. (2004). A review of postpartum depression for the primary care physician. *Southern Medical Journal 97*, 157-161.
- Cox, J. L., Holden, J. M., & Sagovsky, R., (1987). Detection of postpartum depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry, 150*, 782-786.
- Dennis, C. L. (2004). Can we identify mothers at risk for postpartum depression in the immediate postpartum period using the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale? *Journal of Affective Disorders, 78*, 163-169.
- Evins, G. G., & Theofrastous, P. J. (1997). Postpartum depression: A review of postpartum screening. *Primary Care Update Obstetrics and Gynecology, 4*, 241-244.
- Fancher, T., Ton, H., Meyer, O., Ho, T., & Paterniti, D. (2010). Discussing depression with Vietnamese American patients. *Journal Immigrant Minority Health, 12*, 263-266.
- Goyal, D., Wang, E. J., Shen, J., Wong, E. C., & Palaniappan, L. P. (2012). Clinically identified postpartum depression in Asian American mothers. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, & Neonatal Nursing, 41*, 408-416.
- Gress-Smith, J, Luecken, L, Lemery-Chalfant, K., & Howe, R. (2012). Postpartum depression prevalence and impact on infant health, weight, and sleep in low-income and ethnic minority women. *Maternal Child Health Journal, 16*, 887-893.
- Hilton, A., & Skrutkowski, M., (2002). Translating instruments into other languages: Development and testing processes. *Cancer Nursing, 25*(1), 1-7.
- Hock, E., & DeMeis, D. K. (1990). Depression in mothers of infants: The role of maternal employment. *Developmental Psychology, 26*, 285-291.

- Holroyd, E., Chan, S., Lopez, V., & Chen, S. (2013). Chinese women practicing “doing the month”: Intergenerational transfers of maternal health practices. *Singapore Nursing Journal*, 40, 26-29.
- Huang, Y. C., & Mathers N. (2001). Postnatal depression-biological or cultural? A comparative study of postnatal women in the UK and Taiwan. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 33, 279-287.
- Kinzie, J. D., Manson, S. M., Vinh, D., Nguyen, T. L., Bui, A., & Than, P. (1982). Development and validation of a Vietnamese language depression rating scale. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 139, 1276-1281.
- Klainin, P., & Arthur, D. G. (2009). Postpartum depression in Asian cultures: A literature review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 46, 1355-1373.
- Lee, D. T. S., Yip, A. S. K., Chiu, H. F. K., Leung, T. Y. S., Chan, K. P. M., Chau, I. O. L., . . . Chung, T. K. H. (1998). Detecting postnatal depression in Chinese women: Validation of the Chinese version of the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 172, 433-437.
- Lee, D. T. S., Yip, S. K., Chiu, H. F. K., Leung, T. Y. S., Chan, K. P. M., Chau, I. O. L., . . . Chung, T. K. H. (1998). Detecting postnatal depression in Chinese women: Validation of the Chinese version of the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 172, 433-437.
- McQueen, K., Montgomery, P., Lappan-Gracon, S., Evans, M., & Hunter, J. (2008). Evidence-based recommendations for depressive symptoms in postpartum women. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic and Neonatal Nursing*, 37, 127-136.
- Miller, L., & LaRusso, E. (2011). Presenting postpartum depression. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 34, 53-65.
- Niemi, M., Malqvist, M., Giang, K. B., Allebeck, P., & Falkenberg, T. (2013). A narrative review of factors influencing detection and treatment of depression in Vietnam. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, 7, 15. doi:10.1186/1752-4458-7-15
- Pitanupong, J., Liabsuetrakul, T., & Vittayanont, A. (2007). Validation of the Thai Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale for screening postpartum depression. *Psychiatry Research*, 149, 253-259.
- Rosenstock, I. (1974). The Health Belief Model and preventive health behavior. *Health Education Monographs*, 4, 335-385.
- Rosenstock, I. M., Strecher, V. J., & Becker, M. (1988). Social learning theory and the Health Belief Model. *Health Education Quarterly* 5(2), 175-183.
- Small, R., Lumley, J., & Yelland, J. (2003). Cross-cultural experiences of maternal depression: Association and contributing factors for Vietnamese, Turkish and Filipino immigrant women in Victoria, Australia. *Ethnicity and Health*, 8, 189-206.

- Teng, W. H., Hsu, C. S., Shih, S. M., Lu, M. L., Pan, J., & Shen, W. (2005). Screening postpartum depression with the Taiwanese version of the Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale. *Comprehensive Psychiatry, 46*, 262-265.
- U.S. Bureau of the Census. (2010). *The Asian population: 2010*. Retrieved from <http://www.census.gov/2010census/data/>
- Wong, R., Wu, R., Guo, C., Lam, J., & Snowden, L. R. (2012). Culturally sensitive depression assessment for Chinese American immigrants: Development of a comprehensive measure and a screening scale using an item response approach. *Asian American Journal of Psychology, 3*, 230-253.
- Yoo, W., Kwon, M., & Pfeiffer, L. (2013). Influence of communication on colorectal cancer screening: Revisiting the Health Belief Model. *Journal of Communication in Healthcare, 6*, 35-42.
- Youn, J. H., & Jeong, I. S. (2011). Predictive validity of the Postpartum Depression Predictors Inventory-Revised. *Asian Nursing Research, 5*, 210-215.
- Zubaran, C., Schumacher, M., Roxo, M. R., & Foresti, K. (2010). Screening tools for postpartum depression: Validity and cultural dimensions. *African Journal of Psychiatry, 13*, 357-365.

APPENDIX A
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table of Evidence for Nonexperimental Descriptive Studies

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements,	Results of Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Compare perceptions of stigma about depression between Asian Americans (AA) and Caucasians who screen positive for depression. (Fogel & Ford., 2005)	Cross-sectional descriptive study. Stigma beliefs about depression	Internet sample of individuals. Screened positive for depression $N = 68,656$ (AA = 1,839; Caucasian = 66,817)	CES-D: 20 items 5-point Likert scale: 3 types of stigma: 1) "I would be embarrassed if my friends knew I was getting professional help for an emotional problem"; 2) "I would not want my employer to know that I was getting professional help for an emotional problem" and 3) "If I had depression, my family would be disappointed in me."	AA stigma beliefs demonstrated > Caucasian with regard to friends ($p < .001$), employer ($p < .001$) and family ($p < .001$). Stigma belief among AA: male > female in regard to friend and employer but not family; difference in stigma belief among the three age groups (16-29; 30-45; 45-60), less stigma in younger AA. Less stigma leads to increased need for treatment: strongest affect from friend, least from family.	Difference in belief of mental health stigma between AA and Caucasian, especially among younger AA because of acculturation. Difference in levels of stigma belief between male and female in both AA and Caucasian. (p. 474) Limitation: not able to identify specific ethnicity; no valid measurement for acculturation; unable to generalize the finding due to anonymity in data collection.

<p>To establish the prevalence of perinatal mental disorders in Northern Vietnamese women.</p> <p>(Fisher et al., 2010)</p>	<p>Cross sectional survey.</p> <p>Postpartum Depression</p> <p>Generalized anxiety disorder</p>	<p>506 pregnant or postpartum Vietnamese women</p> <p>One rural and one urban community health center in Northern Vietnam</p>	<p>EPDS: cut off score of 12.</p> <p>Clinical specific interviews: structured clinical interview for DSM-IV (SCID)</p>	<p>29.9%: diagnosis with mental disorder.</p> <p>10% during pregnancy</p> <p>13 % postpartum.</p> <p>Rate of depression increase two times in rural area; family violence (from partners or in law); social economic status.</p> <p>No data on seeking treatment for depression</p>	<p>Perinatal disorder: more prevalence in Viet Nam compared to high income countries.</p> <p>Nurturing intimate relationship is protective factors for perinatal mental illness</p> <p>Socioeconomic adversity: major factors in perinatal mental illness in Vietnamese women.</p> <p>Cultural difference in perception of mental illness: mental disorder is not a biological illness.</p> <p>Limitation: cohort come from two different setting → cannot generalize finding.</p> <p>Future research: poverty and violence as risk factors for mental illness among community setting.</p>
---	---	---	--	---	---

Investigate psychometric properties of Chinese translation of QIDS ₁₆ (Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology) and its accuracy in screening or treatment monitoring for depression among Chinese Americans.	Descriptive study. The study examines the characteristics of speech in patient with depression. Participants assessed at: baseline, week 4 and week 8. Independent variables (IV): QIDS ₁₆ Dependent variables (DV): Signs/symptoms of depression.	Participants from behavioral health clinic of South Cove community in Boston's China town. 30 Chinese Americans (18-80) just started or about to begin a new treatment regimen for MDD and had QIDS-C ₁₆ scores of 10+ at baseline. Treatment decided by clinicians (can include psychopharmacology/psychotherapy).	QIDS ₁₆ , QIDS-SR ₁₆ , and QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ (Chinese translation), used to assess criterion symptom domain: sad mood, poor concentration, self-criticism, suicidal ideation, anhedonia, energy/fatigue, sleep disturbance, decrease/increase in appetite/weight, and psychomotor agitation/retardation. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis done to assess the accuracy of the QIDS-SR ₁₆ and QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ .	Baseline: mean (SD, range) for QIDS-SR ₁₆ : 14.2 (4.0; 3-23) QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ : 16.2 (4.0; 10-24) QIDS-C ₁₆ : 14.9 (2.8; 9-20) At week 8: QIDS-SR ₁₆ : 10.0 (4.1; 1-19) QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ : 11.5 (5.4; 1-22) QIDS-C ₁₆ : 9.0 (4.4; 1-19) ROC: criterion for MDD diagnosis using QIDS-SR ₁₆ is 0.78 and QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ is 0.81.	Chinese translations of the QIDS-C ₁₆ , QIDS-SR ₁₆ and QIDS-SR-IVR ₁₆ had adequate psychometric properties in immigrant Chinese Americans. These tools demonstrated screening sensibility and specificity. These tools can be used in routine monitoring of depression symptoms. Limitation: limited sample size; participants predominantly from underserved Chinese immigrants- may not generalize to other groups.
(Yeung et al., 2012)					

<p>To assess association between immigration-related factors and depression, anxiety disorders, suicidal ideation among Chinese Americans.</p> <p>(Zhang et al., 2013)</p>	<p>Cross sectional descriptive study. Depressive disorder, anxiety disorder and suicidal ideation in relation to immigration factors. Immigration factors: nativity status, English-language proficiency and age at time of immigration.</p>	<p>Chinese Americans in data base from the National Latino and Asian American Study (NLAAS) - psychiatric survey (2002-2003) across United States. 284 (47.33%) male and 316 (52.67%) female; ages 18 to 85 years. No weighting analysis of the Chinese sample.</p>	<p>Chinese version of NLAAS (interview). 47% of interview conducted in English. World Health Organization Composite International Diagnostic Interview: assessed depression, and anxiety disorders. Suicidal ideation question: "Have you ever seriously thought about committing suicide (in the past 12 months)?" Immigration factor: nativity status (U.S or China born); English language (excellent, good, fair or poor); immigration age group (<= 12 / 13 - 17 / 18 -34 / 35+ years)</p>	<p>Language proficiency and level of education: no effect in prevalence rates of depressive disorder, anxiety disorder and suicidal ideation. Prevalence of above mental disorders: United States born > than Chinese born. Immigration age groups (<18 vs. ≥ 18): prevalence of depressive disorder (17.95% vs. 7.14%); anxiety disorder (16.24% vs. 6.04%); suicidal ideation (17.52% vs 6.59%).</p>	<p>The important immigration factors: age at the time of immigration and nativity. Acculturation and social forces: effect the psychological well-being of Chinese American. Internalized cultures conflict: perceived as psychological strain lead to depression and anxiety.</p> <p>Limitation: small sample size might lead to false negative result; sample bias due to unweight data; comparing mental disorder among Asian population using Western's measure may underestimate the problem. Valid study: need to look into the differences of Chinese and Vietnamese groups.</p>
--	--	---	---	--	---

<p>To identify postpartum depression's prevalence among Asian and Pacific Islander ethnic groups; to compare with other ethnic groups, and to assess the difference factors contributed to postpartum depression.</p> <p>(Hayes et al., 2010)</p>	<p>Non-experimental cross-sectional descriptive study. Postpartum depression: mood and interest in activities since giving birth. Factors that affect the depression: maternal age, level of education; unintended pregnancy; experienced intimate partner violent; WIC recipient; and illicit drugs used.</p> <p>Estimate prevalence in Black, Chinese, Filipino, Hawaiian, Japanese, Korean, Samoan, White, Hispanic, other Asian, other Pacific Islander, and unknown.</p>	<p>Representative sample: survey data from Hawaii's Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System (PRAMS). Sampling drawn from birth certificate and self-report questionnaire. Women in Hawaii with recent live birth</p> <p>Sample size: 7,154</p>	<p>2 modified questions from the PHQ-2 (depression screening tool):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Since your new baby was born, how often have you felt down, depressed or hopeless? 2. Since your new baby was born, how often have you had little interest or little pleasure in doing things? <p>Likert scale (always, often, sometimes, rarely and never)</p>	<p>All women: 14.5% had SRPDS (higher among Samoan, black, Hawaiian, and Filipino compared to White)</p> <p>Adjusted odds ratios model: 30.3% of all women possible had SRPDS (higher among Chinese, Korean, Filipino and other Pacific Islander)</p> <p>More likely to have SRPDS: women with unintended pregnancy, less education, experienced intimate partner violence, and < 35 years old (pp.769-770).</p>	<p>Strongest predictor for SRPDS: experience of intimate partner violence. Many factors result in postpartum depression related to education: more education → increased resources and coping skills. This might lead to less illicit drugs use and unintended pregnancy. Limitation: self-reported questions about illicit drug used and other sensitive issues subject to social bias; the representative of postpartum depression based on two questions should be used only for screening not diagnosis of depression. Can used the questions in this study to design a screening tool.</p>
---	---	--	---	--	---

<p>To examine racial/ethnic disparities in the diagnosis of PPD.</p> <p>(Liu & Tronick, 2013)</p>	<p>Prospective descriptive study.</p> <p>Depression: White, African American, Asian/Pacific Islander (API), American Indian/Alaskan.</p> <p>Covariates: maternal age, household income, maternal education, nativity and infant age at time of questionnaire completion.</p>	<p>N = 3,732</p> <p>Part of ongoing population based random sampling of New York City (NYC)</p>	<p>Survey questionnaires in English and Spanish: (a) stressful event during pregnancy? (b) At any time during your most recent pregnancy, did the doctor, nurse or other health care worker diagnose you with depression? (c) At any time during your most recent pregnancy, did the doctor, nurse or other health care worker talk with you about “baby blues” or postpartum depression?</p> <p>A yes/no response to surveys.</p>	<p>API: highest rate for PPD (12.4%; p<.05)</p> <p>API: 4.6 times more likely to receive diagnosis of depression than White accounting for socio-demographic factors (p<.001).</p> <p>Profiles of women with PPD diagnoses vs women without diagnoses: vary by race/ethnicity. API (high school graduates, income less than 15,000 annually, higher percentage of unintended pregnancy, more likely to give birth to female infant).</p>	<p>Possibility of differential effects in the risk factors associated with PPD.</p> <p>Risk factors for PPD: different in different race/ethnicity.</p> <p>Universal postpartum depression screening as a single approach: not adequate</p> <p>Provider/patient interaction related to diagnosis of PPD: significantly important.</p> <p>Limitation: Self report → inaccuracies due to recall problem.</p> <p>Different standards for diagnoses.</p> <p>Depression diagnosis: not reflect actual depression rate.</p> <p>Race/ethnicity: proxy for a culture; comprise of heterogeneous group.</p>
---	--	---	--	--	--

Note. AA = Asian American; ANCOVA = analysis of covariance; ANOVA = analysis of variance; API = Asian Pacific Islander; BDI = Beck Depression Inventory; BDI-SF = Beck Depression Inventory-Short Form; CES-D = Center of Epidemiologic Studies-Depression Scale; CIS-R = The revised of Clinical Interview Schedule; DSM-IV = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder 4th edition; ESDS = Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale; GAD = generalized anxiety disorder; HIV-PHC = Human Immunodeficiency Virus- Primary health care; K-10 = Kessler Psychological Distress Scale, SRQ-20 = Self-Reporting Questionnaires-20; LMC = low and middle income countries; MDD = major depressive disorder; NLAAS = national Latino and Asian American study; OR = odds ratio; PDD = Postpartum depression; PDRS = Postpartum Depression Risk Scale; PHQ-10 = Patient Health Questionnaire-10; PHQ-9 = Patient Health Questionnaire-9; PRAMS = Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring system; QIDS-C = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Clinician; QIDS-IVR = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Interactive Voice Response; QIDS-SR = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Self Report; ROC = Receiver Operating Characteristic; SCAN = The Schedule for Clinical Assessment In Neuropsychiatry; SCID-IV = Structure Clinical Interview for DSM-IV; SRPDS = Self-Report Postpartum Depression Symptom; U.S = United State; VDS = Vietnamese Depression Screening Scale; WHO-CIDI = World Health Organization-composite international diagnostic interview.

Table of Evidence for Qualitative Studies

Purpose (Author(s), Year)	Conceptual Theoretical Underpinnings, Design	Sample & setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Perception of depression among Vietnamese American (VA) patients. (Fancher et al., 2009)	Descriptive qualitative study Stigma of depression Depression	11 first and second Vietnamese generation interviewed. Sacramento community, California.	Semi- structure interview. Theme analysis: (a) stigma and face, (b) social function and the role of the family, (c) traditional healing and beliefs about medications, (d) language and culture	VA deny sign and symptoms of depression to save face Depression is associated with poor moral character, spiritual weakness, and improper upbringing of the family. Interdependence relationship: family impact of mental well-being. Depression beliefs: metaphysical imbalance; avoid Western treatment due to strong side effects, afraid to take anti-depressant long term. Language and cultural barriers: communication	Culturally responsive therapy: increase participation and better outcomes of treatment for depression in VA population. Health care providers: minimize stigma by helping with face-saving strategies; addressing social functioning and family roles; incorporate traditional beliefs in treatment plan; optimize language concordance and cultural understanding. Limitation: small sample size, unable to generalize

Note. VA = Vietnamese American.

Table of Evidence for Validated EPDS Translation Tools

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Mann-Whitney U-test	Results of Findings	Author conclusions; Limitations, Notes
Investigate the validity of the Chinese EPDS (Lee et al., 1998)	Prospective cohort design Chinese EPDS, the Chinese version of the General health Questionnaire (GHQ) and the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI).	Prince of Wales Hospital in Hong Kong. 330 women (age 16-42) in postnatal ward of department of obstetrics and gynecology.	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Participants: with no face to face interview- lower GHQ, BDI, and EPDS' scores. ($P < 0.0005$). EPDS moderately correlated with GHQ (Spearman correlation = 0.50, $p < 0.00$) and BDI (Spearman correlation = 0.73, $p < 0.001$). 16 out of 142 scored above the 12/13 cut-off. EPDS concurrent validity with BDI and GHQ scores Cut off scores at 9/10 (sensitivity 82%; specificity 86%). Prevalence at 2 weeks: 5% Prevalence at 6 weeks: 11.3%.	Chinese EPDS: useful screening for PPD Recommended cut off scores: 9/10. Limitations: High attrition rates. Validation limited to six weeks postpartum The performance of EPDS not compared with common screening scales such as GHQ.
	Interview with Chinese non-patient version of Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-III-R (SCID-NP) Minor depression Major depression				

<p>To validate and determine an appropriate cut off score on the Thai EPDS (Pitanupong et al., 2005)</p>	<p>Prospective cohort of postpartum women. Thai EPDS Minor depression Major depression Clinical interview based on DSM-IV diagnosis criteria.</p>	<p>351 postpartum women. University hospital in the South of Thailand (October of 2003 till July of 2004)</p>	<p>The indices of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) and the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve.</p>	<p>The mean age: 27.9 years. One third of the women: primigravidas. 97% married; 89% Buddhist, 37% low social economic status (SES). 50% lived with parents or in-laws. 1% :major depression 10% minor depression Internal consistencies of EPDS: 0.81. Cut off score 6/7: sensitivity 74%; specificity 74%; PPV 26% and NPV 96%. Cut off score 12/13: sensitivity 34%; specificity 97%; PPV 59% and NPV 92%. 75% depressed women reported anxious and not coping. One-fifth of depressed women: self-harm thought.</p>	<p>Thai EPDS: able to discriminate depressed and non-depressed women. Cut off scores of 6/7: identified postpartum women with minor and major depressive disorders. Limitations: Unable to generalize because of the setting. Postpartum period limited to 6-8 weeks. Sample size for validation is small. The validation of the EPDS for major depression not indicated.</p>
--	---	---	---	---	---

Develop Taiwanese version of the EPDS; evaluate its validity; estimate prevalence of PPD among Taiwanese women. (Teng et al., 2005)	Prospective cohort study. Thai EPDS BDI-II Mini-international Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) and DSM-IV. Depression	203 postpartum women in maternity ward of department of obstetrics and gynecology. Taipei Medical University and Wan Fang hospital.	ROC: cut off point for the EPDS. Pearson correlation: compare EPDS and BDI-II. X^2 test: associate risk factors for PPD	Prevalence of psychiatric disorder: 11.8% diagnosis with depressive disorder; 12.3% with anxiety disorder; 2% with panic disorder. Prevalence of PPD: 10.3% Validation of Taiwanese EPDS: Internal consistency is satisfactory (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.87$) EPDS moderately correlated with BDI-II (Spearman correlation = 0.77, $p < .01$) Cut off point 12/13: sensitivity 96%; specificity 85%; PPD 46%; and NPD 99%.	Taiwanese EPDS correlate with clinical diagnosis. EPDS: validated to use for early detection and intervention of PPD. Prevalence of PPD: 11.8% same as study by Lee et al (11.7%) but lower than reported by Chen et al (40%) Limitations: cannot be generalized: sample from hospital not a large-scale community clinic; onset date of PPD not defined: limit only to six weeks postpartum
--	--	--	---	--	---

Development and validation of the EPDS. (Cox et al., 1987)	Prospective cohort study. EPDS SPI interview RDC Depression	63 postpartum women. Health center in Livingston	Cronbach's alpha: estimate of reliability t-test: difference of pre-test and post-test score of EPDS	Sensitivity 85%; specificity 77%; Alpha coefficient 0.87; EPDS-1 mean scores = 15.8; EPDS-2 mean scores = 9.8; $t = 3.71$; $P = 0.002$.	EPDS: satisfactory validity, split half reliability, and sensitive to changes in severity of depression over time. Scale is accepted by postpartum women. Sensitivity and specificity: increased if form completed with present of family members. Cut off scores of 9/10: appropriate for use in primary care setting. Limitation: Cannot generalize to other clinical settings or other population.
---	---	---	---	--	---

Development and Validation of a Vietnamese-language depression rating scale. (Kinzie et al., 1982)	Translation and modification of Beck Depression Inventory (BDI): 45 items → 15 items Two groups' comparison: Quasi experiment. Diagnosis with depression. Somatic depression symptoms Vietnamese Depression scale (VDS)	Psychiatric index group (N = 21) Matched community sample (N = 44) Psychiatric outpatient clinic in Portland Oregon. Vietnamese refugee community in Portland	15 items vs 45 items VDS: test for depression symptoms Chi-square tests: sampling distribution between groups. Correlation coefficient: relationship between the 15 items test and the 45 items test.	Of the 45 items: three failed to differentiate the patient and the control groups. Majority of items : highly significant differences between two groups (chi-square tests, $p < .001$) 4 items: psychophysiological symptoms 23 items: Vietnamese descriptions of cognitive, affective, and somatic indications of depression. Correlation between two test: the 15 items test 96% of the variance of the sum of the scores on the 45 original items (R = .98; $p < .0001$)	No equivalent between Western and Vietnamese notion of guilt. Western definition of depression: not include desperation or “going crazy” that characterized by the community group. Awkwardness of the English words with translation: the differences in thought, behavior and feeling.
---	---	--	---	--	--

Note. BDI = Beck Depression Inventory; BDI-II = Beck Depression Inventory 2nd edition; DSM-III-R = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder 3rd edition Revision; DSM-IV = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder 4th edition; EPDS = Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale; GHQ = General Health Questionnaire; MINI = Mini-international Neuropsychiatric Interview; NPV = Negative Predictive Value; PPD = Postpartum Depression; PPV = Positive Predictive Value; RDC = Researcher Diagnostic Criteria; ROC = Receiver Operating Characteristic curve; SPI = Standardized Psychiatric Interview; VDS = Vietnamese Depression Scale

Table of Evidence for Meta-Analysis Studies

Purpose of the Literature Review. (Author(s), year)	Literature Search approach; Number of Studies Review	Selection Process	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitation; Notes
Examine accuracy of depression screening tools in low and middle income countries. (Akena et al., 2012)	PUBMED, COCHRANE library, AIDSLINE and PSYCH-info databases: studies published in English. 19 studies included.	Studies with outcome of interest: depression screening instrument then a formal diagnostic instrument to all screened patients; conducted in non-mental health facilities and LMIC; reported sensitivity/specificity and predictive value of the screening instrument compared with diagnostic standard. Three authors independently determine the inclusion and exclusion of studies. Another author rated quality of the included studies (p. 188)	10 studies rated good quality; one -fair, 8 studies-acceptable. 11.1%-53% prevalence of depression in LMIC. Brief and long screening instruments: acceptable accuracy. Validated five instruments within HIV settings. Statistically significant various between studies. Brief screening instrument: BDI-SF; PHQ-10; and K-10. Longer instrument: CES-D, SRQ-20 (p. 193)	Brief depression screening instruments as accurate as the long one in general and HIV-PHC. Brief scales might be better than long one due to time issues. Brief scales do not include whole spectrum of depression symptoms → need for a detailed diagnostic tools to follow (p. 194) Limitation: not reviewed screening instruments tailoring the whole range of psychiatric morbidity. Inclusion of scales which screened for depression and anxiety would be more informative (p. 195) Useful information to consider in developing a cultural sensitive screening tools.

Review factors influencing detection and treatment of depression in Vietnam. (Niemi et al., 2013)	Pub Med; CINAHL Six relevant Vietnamese peer-review research journals. 20 studies reviewed.	Studies included: culturally and contextually specific risk factors for depression; depression treatment seeking and or treatment acceptability; depression screening among Vietnamese patients.	Identified two Vietnamese depression screening scale with. One was validated and one was not. Overlap between affective and somatic experiences. Neurasthenia as depression symptoms among Vietnamese patients. Postpartum depression risk factors: hostile behaviors from the in law family; worrying about the wellbeing of newborn; husband extra marital affairs. Barriers to seek care: not openly speak of depression symptoms; lack of recognition of depressive symptoms; depression sign of immature and weakness.	Screening for depression in Vietnamese population: need to be culturally adapted; focus on somatic symptoms; risk factors associated with social adversity. Effective treatment plan: incorporate the traditional medicine and meditation. Future studies: clarify neurasthenia (nervous breakdown) as symptoms of depression among Vietnamese population Limitations: reviewed process did not allow pooling of the results.
--	---	--	---	--

Note. AA = Asian American; ANCOVA = analysis of covariance; ANOVA = analysis of variance; BDI = Beck Depression Inventory; BDI-SF = Beck Depression Inventory-Short Form; CES-D = Center of Epidemiologic Studies-Depression Scale; CIS-R = The revised of Clinical Interview Schedule; DSM-IV = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder 4th edition; ESDS = Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale; GAD = generalized anxiety disorder; HIV-PHC = Human Immunodeficiency Virus- Primary health care; K-10 = Kessler Psychological Distress Scale, SRQ-20 = Self-Reporting Questionnaires-20; LIMC = low and middle income countries; MDD = major depressive disorder; NLAAS = national Latino and Asian American study; OR = odds ratio; PDD = Postpartum depression; PDRS = Postpartum Depression Risk Scale; PHQ-10 = Patient Health Questionnaire-10; PHQ-9 = Patient Health Questionnaire-9; PRAMS = Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring system; QIDS-C = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Clinician; QIDS-IVR = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Interactive Voice Response; QIDS-SR = Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology-Self Report; ROC = Receiver Operating Characteristic; SCAN = The Schedule for Clinical Assessment In Neuropsychiatry; SCID-IV = Structure Clinical Interview for DSM-IV; SRPDS = Self-Report Postpartum Depression Symptom; U.S = United State; VDS = Vietnamese Depression Screening Scale; WHO-CIDI = World Health Organization-composite international diagnostic interview.

APPENDIX B

EDINBURG POSTNATAL DEPRESSION SCALE (EPDS)

Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale¹ (EPDS)

Name: _____ Address: _____

Your Date of Birth: _____

Baby's Date of Birth: _____ Phone: _____

As you are pregnant or have recently had a baby, we would like to know how you are feeling. Please check the answer that comes closest to how you have felt **IN THE PAST 7 DAYS**, not just how you feel today.

Here is an example, already completed.

I have felt happy:

- Yes, all the time
- Yes, most of the time This would mean: "I have felt happy most of the time" during the past week.
- No, not very often Please complete the other questions in the same way.
- No, not at all

In the past 7 days:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>1. I have been able to laugh and see the funny side of things</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> As much as I always could</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not quite so much now</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely not so much now</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not at all</p> | <p>*6. Things have been getting on top of me</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, most of the time I haven't been able to cope at all</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sometimes I haven't been coping as well as usual</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, most of the time I have coped quite well</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, I have been coping as well as ever</p> |
| <p>2. I have looked forward with enjoyment to things</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> As much as I ever did</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Rather less than I used to</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Definitely less than I used to</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hardly at all</p> | <p>*7. I have been so unhappy that I have had difficulty sleeping</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, most of the time</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sometimes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not very often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all</p> |
| <p>*3. I have blamed myself unnecessarily when things went wrong</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, most of the time</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, some of the time</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not very often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, never</p> | <p>*8. I have felt sad or miserable</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, most of the time</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, quite often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not very often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all</p> |
| <p>4. I have been anxious or worried for no good reason</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hardly ever</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sometimes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, very often</p> | <p>*9. I have been so unhappy that I have been crying</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, most of the time</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, quite often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Only occasionally</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, never</p> |
| <p>*5. I have felt scared or panicky for no very good reason</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, quite a lot</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, sometimes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, not much</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all</p> | <p>*10. The thought of harming myself has occurred to me</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, quite often</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hardly ever</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Never</p> |

Administered/Reviewed by _____ Date _____

¹Source: Cox, J.L., Holden, J.M., and Sagovsky, R. 1987. Detection of postnatal depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 150:782-786 .

²Source: K. L. Wisner, B. L. Parry, C. M. Piontek, Postpartum Depression N Engl J Med vol. 347, No 3, July 18, 2002, 194-199

Users may reproduce the scale without further permission providing they respect copyright by quoting the names of the authors, the title and the source of the paper in all reproduced copies.

Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale¹ (EPDS)

Postpartum depression is the most common complication of childbearing.² The 10-question Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) is a valuable and efficient way of identifying patients at risk for "perinatal" depression. The EPDS is easy to administer and has proven to be an effective screening tool.

Mothers who score above 13 are likely to be suffering from a depressive illness of varying severity. The EPDS score should not override clinical judgment. A careful clinical assessment should be carried out to confirm the diagnosis. The scale indicates how the mother has felt *during the previous week*. In doubtful cases it may be useful to repeat the tool after 2 weeks. The scale will not detect mothers with anxiety neuroses, phobias or personality disorders.

Women with postpartum depression need not feel alone. They may find useful information on the web sites of the National Women's Health Information Center <www.4women.gov> and from groups such as Postpartum Support International <www.chss.iup.edu/postpartum> and Depression after Delivery <www.depressionafterdelivery.com>.

SCORING

QUESTIONS 1, 2, & 4 (without an *)

Are scored 0, 1, 2 or 3 with top box scored as 0 and the bottom box scored as 3.

QUESTIONS 3, 5-10 (marked with an *)

Are reverse scored, with the top box scored as a 3 and the bottom box scored as 0.

Maximum score: 30
Possible Depression: 10 or greater
Always look at item 10 (suicidal thoughts)

Users may reproduce the scale without further permission, providing they respect copyright by quoting the names of the authors, the title, and the source of the paper in all reproduced copies.

Instructions for using the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale:

1. The mother is asked to check the response that comes closest to how she has been feeling in the previous 7 days.
2. All the items must be completed.
3. Care should be taken to avoid the possibility of the mother discussing her answers with others. (Answers come from the mother or pregnant woman.)
4. The mother should complete the scale herself, unless she has limited English or has difficulty with reading.

¹Source: Cox, J.L., Holden, J.M., and Sagovsky, R. 1987. Detection of postnatal depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 150:782-786.

²Source: K. L. Wisner, B. L. Parry, C. M. Piontek, Postpartum Depression N Engl J Med vol. 347, No 3, July 18, 2002, 194-199

APPENDIX C

CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN PILOT STUDY

I volunteer to participate in a research project conducted by Thu Pham from California State University of Long Beach. I understand that the project is designed to gather information about sign and symptoms of depression after giving birth. I will be one of approximately 50 people to fill out the questionnaire to assess for depression in this project.

1. My participation in this project is voluntary. I understand that I will not be paid for my participation. I may withdraw and discontinue participation at any time without penalty.
2. I understand that the questionnaire is a list of self-report symptoms of depression. If however, I feel uncomfortable in any way while filling out the questionnaire, I have the right to not fill out the question.
3. Participation involves filling out three set of questionnaires. It will last approximately 15 minutes. I will do this by myself not asking any family members.
4. I understand that researcher will not identify me by name in any reports using information obtained from the questionnaire and that my confidentiality as a participant in this study will remain secure. Subsequent uses of records and data will be subject to standard data use policy which protect the anonymity of individuals and institutions.
5. I understand that this research study has been reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for study that involves human subjects: social

and behavioral sciences committee at California State University Long Beach.

For research problem and question regarding subjects the Institute Review Board can be contacted through 562-985-2502

6. I have read and understand the explanation provided to me. I have had all of my questions answered to my satisfaction, and I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
7. I have been given of this consent form.

Participant signature

Date

Participant Print Name

Signature of the

Investigator

For further information please contact: Thu Pham at
thupham7lovejesus@csuf.edu

APPENDIX D
DEMOGRAPHIC DATA SURVEY

Please complete the following questions about yourself:

1. Age: _____
2. Marital status: _____Single _____Married
3. Highest Educational Level: _____
4. Employment status: _____Full time _____Part time _____Unemployed
5. Length of stay in America _____
6. Preferred language _____Vietnamese _____English
7. Living condition: _____With in-law _____With extended family
8. Number of pregnancy _____
9. Complication during pregnancy and delivery: ____yes ____ no
If yes, what is the complication? _____
10. Route of current delivery _____Spontaneous vaginal delivery _____Cesarean

APPENDIX E

VIETNAMESE EDINBURG POSTNATAL DEPRESSION SCALE (VEPDS)

Thang điểm Edinburgh đo độ trầm cảm sau khi sinh (EPDS)

Số ghi danh: _____

Dù quý vị đang mang thai hay vừa sinh em bé, chúng tôi muốn biết quý vị đang cảm thấy thế nào. Xin hãy đánh dấu vào câu trả lời gần đúng nhất với những gì quý vị đã cảm thấy trong vòng 7 ngày qua, không chỉ là những gì quý vị cảm thấy hôm nay.

Đây là một ví dụ mà đã được hoàn tất:

Tôi cảm thấy vui vẻ:

Vâng, đa phần là vậy

Vâng, thỉnh thoảng

Không, không thường xuyên.

Hoàn toàn không.

Điều này có nghĩa là "tôi đa phần cảm thấy vui vẻ" trong suốt một tuần qua.

Xin hãy hoàn tất những câu hỏi khác như cách này.

Trong vòng 7 ngày qua:

1. Tôi đã có thể cười và nhìn thấy khía cạnh hài hước của mọi việc:

- Nhiều đến mức tôi có thể
- Không còn nhiều như trước nữa
- Chắc chắn không còn nhiều nữa
- Hoàn toàn không.

2. Tôi đã ở trong trạng thái trông chờ để hưởng thụ mọi việc:

- Nhiều như trước vậy
- Có vẻ ít hơn trước đây
- Chắc chắn không còn nhiều như trước
- Hầu như là không

3. Tôi đã tự đổ lỗi cho chính mình mỗi khi có vấn đề nan giải*:

- Vâng. Luôn luôn.
- Vâng, đa số là như vậy.
- Không, không thường xuyên.
- Hoàn toàn không.

4. Tôi đã cảm thấy hồi hộp và lo lắng dù không có lý do chính đáng nào:

- Hoàn toàn không
- Hầu như là không
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Vâng, rất thường xuyên

5. Tôi đã cảm thấy sợ hãi và hoang sơ dù không có lý do chính đáng nào*:

- Vâng, nhiều lắm
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Không, không thường xuyên.
- Hoàn toàn không.

6. Mọi việc đã trở nên quá sức chịu đựng của tôi*:

- Vâng, đa phần là tôi cảm thấy không thể chịu đựng được một chút nào
- Vâng, tôi thỉnh thoảng không thể chịu đựng tốt như bình thường nữa
- Không, tôi đa phần thích nghi rất tốt
- Không, tôi vẫn thích nghi tốt như trước đây

7. Tôi đã cảm thấy buồn bã và nó đã dẫn đến tình trạng mất ngủ*:

- Vâng, đa phần là vậy
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Không, không thường xuyên.
- Hoàn toàn không.

8. Tôi đã cảm thấy buồn bã và toàn thân đau nhức một cách vô cớ*:

- Vâng, đa phần là vậy
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Không, không thường xuyên.
- Hoàn toàn không.

9. Tôi đã cảm thấy rất buồn một cách vô cớ và tôi đã khóc*:

- Vâng, đa phần là vậy
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Chỉ một vài lần thôi
- Hoàn toàn không.

10. Tôi đã từng nghĩ đến việc làm nguy hiểm hoặc tử vong cho chính mình hoặc em bé*:

- Vâng, đa phần là vậy
- Vâng, thỉnh thoảng
- Hầu như là không
- Hoàn toàn không

Nguồn:

¹ Cox, J.L., Holden, J.M., and Sagovsky, R. 1987. Detection of postnatal depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 150:782-786.

² K. L. Wisner, B. L. Parry, C. M. Piontek, Postpartum Depression N Engl J Med vol. 347, No 3, July 18, 2002, 194-199

Người sử dụng có thể thử dụng thang điểm này không cần sự cho phép, chỉ cần cho thấy trích dẫn tên của các tác giả, tiêu đề, và nguồn của những tài liệu.

Thang điểm Edinburgh đo độ trầm cảm sau khi sanh (EPDS)

Chứng trầm cảm sau khi sanh là một trong những phức tạp phổ biến nhất trong quá trình sinh sản.²Thang điểm Edinburgh đo độ trầm cảm sau khi sanh (EPDS) gồm 10 câu hỏi là công cụ khảo nghiệm hiệu quả những bệnh nhân với nguy cơ mắc chứng trầm cảm sau khi sanh. Thang điểm Edinburgh đo độ trầm cảm sau khi sanh rất dễ để theo dõi, và đã được chứng minh rằng đây là công cụ khảo nghiệm hiệu quả.

Những người mẹ nào có số điểm trên 13 có thể đang có chứng trầm cảm với mức độ nặng. Số điểm từ thang điểm Edinburgh không được đánh giá cao hơn những chẩn bệnh của bác sĩ. Bệnh nhân cần được khám bệnh cẩn thận hơn để có thể được chẩn bệnh một cách chính xác. Thang điểm này thu thập những triệu chứng của người mẹ trong tuần vừa qua. Trong những trường hợp vẫn còn mơ hồ, sử dụng thang điểm này sau 2 tuần nữa vẫn rất hữu ích. Thang điểm sẽ không nhận dạng những người mẹ với các chứng rối loạn thần kinh lo âu, những chứng sợ hãi hoặc ám ảnh, hoặc rối loạn nhân cách.

Những người phụ nữ mắc chứng trầm cảm sau khi sanh không nên cảm thấy mình đơn độc. Họ có thể tìm được những thông tin hữu ích trên những trang mạng, như National Women's Health Information Center <www.4women.gov>, hoặc Postpartum Support International <www.chss.iup.edu/postpartum>, và Depression after Delivery www.depressionafterdelivery.com

CHẤM ĐIỂM

CÁC CÂU HỎI 1, 2, & 4 (không có dấu *)

Được chấm điểm như sau: 0, 1, 2 hoặc 3 với ô đầu tiên là 0 điểm và ô cuối cùng là 3 điểm.

CÁC CÂU HỎI 3, 5 -> 10 (được đánh dấu *)

Được chấm điểm ngược lại, với ô đầu tiên là 3 điểm và ô cuối cùng là 0 điểm.

Điểm tối đa: 30

Mức điểm cho thấy có thể bị chứng trầm cảm: 10 điểm hoặc cao hơn 10 điểm

Luôn lưu ý đến mục số 10 (những suy nghĩ gây tử vong đến bản thân)

Người sử dụng có thể thử dụng thang điểm này không cần sự cho phép, chỉ cần cho thấy trích dẫn tên của các tác giả, tiêu đề, và nguồn của những tài liệu.

Hướng dẫn sử dụng mức thang Edinburgh đo độ trầm cảm sau sinh:

1. Người mẹ được yêu cầu đánh dấu vào những câu trả lời gần đúng nhất với những gì họ đã cảm thấy trong vòng 7 ngày qua.
2. Tất cả những câu hỏi phải được trả lời hoàn tất.
3. Sự giám sát là cần thiết để tránh trường hợp các bà mẹ thảo luận về câu trả lời của họ với nhau. (Ví dụ: trả lời giống những người mẹ hoặc những người phụ nữ đang mang thai khác).
4. Các bà mẹ nên trả lời câu hỏi một mình mà không tham vấn ý kiến của bất kỳ ai

Nguồn:

¹Cox, J.L., Holden, J.M., and Sagovsky, R. 1987. Detection of postnatal depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 150:782-786.

²K. L. Wisner, B. L. Parry, C. M. Piontek, Postpartum Depression N Engl J Med vol. 347, No 3, July 18, 2002, 194-199